

Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica de Tulancingo

Ivy Barrera García¹, Raymundo Lozano Rosales², Gabriela Ortiz Cordero³

^{1,2,3} Research and Postgraduate Master's Degree in Organizational Management, Universidad Politécnica de Tulancingo, Tulancingo de Bravo, Hidalgo, Mexico

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
27 March 2025

ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to identify the organizational management strategies that impact decision-making at the executive level, specifically in correspondence management (CM) at the Universidad Tecnológica de Tulancingo (UTT) in Hidalgo, Mexico. CM is based on the Archives Law of the State of Hidalgo and includes the reception, registration, distribution, and dispatch of documents to improve transparency and efficiency. Archival records and organizational management are key resources for strategic decision-making.

This study employs a quantitative, descriptive, non-experimental methodology with a cross-sectional, field-based design. The research focuses on 78 heads of department and coordinators, using Likert-scale questionnaires (reliability = 0.940, Cronbach's alpha). The findings indicate that the majority of respondents have a solid understanding of the Archives Law, and many express confidence in its application. Most perceive the CM as effective and well-integrated into daily operations, considering training in this area highly relevant. Compliance with the Archives Law is evident in the daily receipt of correspondence, with the majority of respondents acknowledging the timely and proper handling of documents. However, a small percentage indicated areas for improvement. To improve the CM, several solutions are proposed: implementing an automated document management system, staff training, continuous audits, user satisfaction assessments, improved internal communication, adequate resource allocation, and performance indicators. Ensuring efficient and structured communication is crucial for making informed decisions, optimizing time and resources, and, above all, improving organizational effectiveness.

Corresponding Author:
Raymundo Lozano Rosales

KEYWORDS: Administration, correspondence, strategies, organizational management

I. INTRODUCTION

In the academic context, efficient correspondence management is essential for the proper functioning of educational institutions. The UTT faces the challenge of optimizing this administrative process to improve its organizational performance. Correspondence at a university encompasses a wide range of documents, including internal communications, student applications, and agreements with other institutions. Proper administration not only impacts daily operations but also its ability to meet its strategic objectives. According to Rojas (2020), correspondence management from an operational efficiency and data management perspective can significantly contribute to the improvement of these processes. Therefore, it is essential to explore and analyze organizational management strategies at the executive

level that can be implemented to optimize correspondence management at the UTT.

Organizational management at the executive level is crucial for optimizing communication within the company. Strategic decisions made by senior management can significantly influence the efficiency and effectiveness of these processes (Henao, 2020). Therefore, it is important to explore and analyze organizational management strategies that can be implemented to improve communication at the UTT.

The purpose of this research is to identify and propose organizational management strategies at the executive level to optimize document management at the Universidad Tecnológica de Tulancingo (UTT). It seeks to implement tools and practices that allow for efficient correspondence

management, reducing errors and response times, which will improve both the quality of internal and external information. To this end, a comprehensive review of the literature on organizational management and correspondence management (CM) will be conducted, as well as surveys directed at department heads and administrative staff at the university. The results will provide a clear picture of current challenges and possible solutions, contributing to the development of adequate document control in each area. With these strategies, the UTT is expected to strengthen its administrative performance and enhance its capacity to fulfill its educational mission within the context of educational institutions.

II. BODY OF THE TEXT

Organizational management is a crucial issue in both the private and public sectors, according to an article from the Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México, the economic and political changes of recent decades have driven important transformations in government management, Contreras (2010).

Furthermore, a study by the Universidad Tecnológica de Bolívar highlights the importance of innovation in organizational management and innovation management, which it defines as the set of strategies and methodologies that an organization establishes to systematically innovate and create value, Hernández (2015).

Recent research highlights the importance of organizational management in different educational settings. Rojas (2021) found that management positively impacts school coexistence in public secondary schools by improving communication and varying according to the size of the institution. On the other hand, Fernandini (2022) points out that proper management of internal communication is crucial for teamwork in the educational field.

The correspondence unit plays a central role in document management, ensuring the efficient reception and distribution of communications within the organization (Rodríguez, 2023). Furthermore, Hernández (2020) highlights the importance of archival heritage for social research, emphasizing the need for its preservation and dissemination. In Mexico, the General Archives Law promotes transparency and access to information, guaranteeing fundamental rights.

Document management in universities, according to Mero et al. (2021), is essential for the conservation of documents and institutional memory, while Sosa (2022) highlights the importance of coordinated and homogeneous processes in information management. The implementation of an Institutional Archive System facilitates knowledge management in organizations, improving decision-making and competitiveness. Sosa et al. (2022) refer that this system, although not mandatory for private organizations, promotes a beneficial archival culture.

Santos (2020) developed a web-based correspondence management system that optimizes administrative processes and improves the user experience with an intuitive interface. Correspondence management is essential for administrative decision-making. Balderas et al. (2022) highlighted the problems at CONALEP Tabasco due to the lack of a centralized correspondence management system, which complicates the identification of incidents and affects decision-making. The appropriate use of methodologies can improve these processes.

Pilataxi (2020) evaluated how document management and archiving techniques impact the proper handling of information, ensuring authenticity, reliability, integrity, and availability of documents. Cáceres (2020) identified problems in document management at the Technical University of the North and proposed a manual of operational tools to improve it. Riera (2020) described the Ogikdocs document management system in Logikard, which facilitates the creation and management of documents through a three-level process map.

Similarly, Castillo et al. (2021) outlined general requirements for a document management system at the University of Havana, promoting transparency and accountability. Soria (2020) highlighted the need for a document management system at the University of Otavalo to improve academic and administrative processes. Lacunza et al. (2021) pointed out the need to modernize document management at the National University of La Plata, considering technological solutions for remote work and the legal security of digital files.

Mocetón (2022) highlights the importance of document management to guarantee access to public and state information, based on principles of transparency and organization. This management applies to both public and private entities that offer public services. Berdugo (2016) analyzed two document management systems in Colombia that comply with current legislation, seeking effective solutions and replicable features in other institutions.

Optimization, according to the Royal Spanish Academy (RAE, 2024), involves finding the best way to carry out an activity. Vinueza (2020) considers the optimization of resources and administrative management in the health sector as a strategic tool to improve services and avoid sanctions. Cuesta (2023) contributed to systematizing the optimization of human capital in companies, using technology and process innovation. Salazar (2022) focused his research on optimizing performance in a steel company, identifying strategies to improve administrative management.

Roque's (2012) project, carried out in Pachuca de Soto, Hidalgo, aimed to design a comprehensive document system model for higher education institutions in Mexico. This system provides theoretical and methodological archival tools for document organization and control. The research included the development of instruments necessary for the

“Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica De Tulancingo”

system's operation, considering all stages of the document life cycle, from its reception or creation to its final disposition. The establishment of correspondence, processing, concentration, and historical archive units was proposed, based on archival theory, regulations, and national and international guidelines. Based on these regulations, the construction of a regulatory framework for higher education institutions was proposed.

According to Kyocera Document Solutions México (2020), artificial intelligence algorithms allow many processes to be automated to streamline workflows. They highlight AI's ability to classify and process information at a much faster speed than humans, improving productivity and efficiency in document management.

Likewise, according to The Digital Age (2024), AI is transforming document management by automating document classification, indexing, and information searching. Specific use cases are mentioned, highlighting AI's ability to improve accuracy and reduce response times in document management.

Technological support is relevant in the management of Directors in the administrative, pedagogical, and curricular fields with a strategic guideline in organizational communication. The objective is to determine whether the use of ICT and organizational communication influences the Management of Directors (Tineo, Mehan, 2021).

As Medina's research (2021) shows, it aims to explain how strategic planning is important for the management of an organization. It is based on a review of documents and articles published in Ibero-American databases over ten years (2011-2020), such as REDID, SCIELO, DOAJ, CLASE, and REDALYC. The main conclusion is that strategic planning helps managers identify the company's priorities and decide on the actions necessary to fulfill the organization's mission and objectives.

Another study analyzes how the organization is carried out for graduate studies in universities at Zulia, Venezuela. The results showed that organizational management indicators suggest improvement actions, especially in times of sociopolitical crisis and health emergency. Organizational management is described as organized and planned, although with weaknesses in the resource dimension, which affects the achievement of goals, although not significantly in the optimization of administrative management. In conclusion, organizational management is influenced by social, environmental, and economic factors, which impact the decisions and leadership styles of managers (Ramírez et al., 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The methodology is based on a quantitative approach, using numerical and statistical methods to interpret data and identify patterns, trends, and relationships. It also collects and analyzes data objectively, designing appropriate surveys to

assess document processing efficiency and user satisfaction at the UTT.

This research employed non-probability convenience sampling, selecting 78 people from among directors, heads of departments, and coordinators at the Universidad Tecnológica de Tulancingo (UTT) as study subjects. This sampling technique was chosen due to the specific nature of the study, which requires the participation of individuals with direct knowledge and experience in CM within the institution. Despite the limitations inherent in the lack of randomization, this method allowed for the collection of accurate and relevant information from key stakeholders in the university's document management.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument, a two-phase validation process was carried out:

Content validation: A review was conducted by experts in organizational management and document administration. These specialists evaluated the relevance, clarity, and adequacy of each questionnaire item in relation to the study objectives, suggesting improvements in the wording and eliminating potential biases in the questions.

Pilot test: The questionnaire was administered to a small group of 19 participants with similar characteristics to the final sample, allowing for the identification of potential ambiguities and problems in question interpretation. Based on the feedback obtained, adjustments were made to improve item comprehension and accuracy.

The reliability of the questionnaire was measured using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.940, indicating a high level of internal consistency and ensuring the reliability of the responses. This result supports the use of the questionnaire as a valid instrument for assessing correspondence management at the UTT.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques and content analysis, taking advantage of the specialized Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software for the analysis of quantitative responses, identifying patterns and trends that allow determining the most effective strategies for CM.

The confidentiality and anonymity of participants were ensured at all times, and their informed consent was obtained before the survey was administered. The data collected was handled in accordance with applicable ethical and legal regulations.

This methodological approach allowed us to measure the efficiency and effectiveness of document management strategies and provide practical solutions to improve the centralization, organization, and management of documents at the UTT.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION, AND DISCUSSION

As Figure 1 shows, the majority of respondents consider themselves to have an acceptable level of knowledge of the

“Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica De Tulancingo”

Archives Law, at 61.5%. This suggests significant familiarity with the topic among respondents. This is crucial because it indicates that most respondents have a solid knowledge base and are likely to be able to apply the Law in their respective roles. It is also important to mention that a significant 30.8% of respondents feel very confident in their knowledge of the Archives Law. This shows that almost a third of respondents are not only familiar with the Law but also have a high degree of confidence in its understanding and application. This may indicate the presence of individuals highly skilled in managing archives according to current regulations.

Figura 1.
Conocimiento de la Ley de Archivos

Nota: La grafica muestra el conocimiento que se tiene de la Ley de Archivos del Estado de Hidalgo para su aplicación en el manejo de la AC.

A large majority with 61.5% agree that adequate information has been provided, and 34.6% Totally agree, indicating that a significant proportion are completely confident in the effectiveness of communication as shown in Figure 2. There is positive approval regarding the effectiveness of communication on correspondence management, with a strong perception of good performance in this area and high overall satisfaction among respondents.

Figura 2.
Conocimiento de la información de Administración de correspondencia

Nota: La grafica muestra si el personal de la UTT conoce lo que es la AC.

The majority of respondents are completely sure that they base their activities on correspondence management, as shown by 61.5% who agree, and 30.8% who Totally agree. There is a strong tendency to consider correspondence

management as a central and well-established practice in daily work, with a high degree of identification among respondents, as shown in Figure 3. General satisfaction and positive perception are predominant in this aspect.

Figura 3.
Desempeño de las actividades en base a la Administración de correspondencia

Nota: La grafica refleja el uso de la AC en las actividades diarias.

Training is viewed very positively in correspondence management. A significant majority of respondents (88.4%) consider the training relevant, with 61.5% agreeing and 26.9% totally agreeing. This approval reflects a high appreciation and perception of the training's relevance, as shown in Figure 4. A small percentage of respondents (7.7%) remain neutral, indicating some doubts, and 3.8% express disagreement. However, the absence of "totally disagree" responses suggests that there is no strong opposition to the training.

Figura 4.
La capacitación de la Coordinación de Archivos es pertinente a nivel directivo en la Administración de Correspondencia.

Nota: La grafica determina la disposición de recibir capacitación en materia de AC.

With 80.7% there is a high level of compliance with the Law, the Archives Law is put into practice in the daily reception of correspondence and a significant portion of the 26.9% is completely sure of this implementation, compliance and application of the Archives Law in most of the respondents' work areas is considered a well-established

“Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica De Tulancingo”

practice in the daily reception of correspondence, as shown in Figure 5.

Figura 5. La implementación de la Ley de Archivos en el área destinada a la recepción diaria de correspondencia.

Nota: La grafica refleja la aplicación de la Ley de Archivos en la AC de la UTT.

The following shows that 84.6% of respondents believe that correspondence is received in a timely manner, indicating high efficiency in its handling. 11.5% expressed indifference, which may reflect a lack of clear perception, and a small 3.8% disagreed with the statement, pointing to possible areas for improvement. No respondents completely disagreed, suggesting a lack of significant rejection, as shown in Figure 6. Overall, the perception is positive, favoring the effectiveness of the process.

Figura 6. La correspondencia correspondiente al área es recibida y debidamente turnada en tiempo y forma.

Nota: La grafica muestra el manejo de la comunicación a nivel directivo de la UTT.

A percentage of 69.3% of respondents have a favorable perception of conducting periodic audits in mail management, with 46.2% agreeing and 23.1% totally agreeing. This assessment highlights the importance of audits as a control and efficiency mechanism. However, 23.1% of respondents are indifferent, which may reflect a lack of information or interest in the topic. In addition, only 7.7% expressed disagreement, indicating minimal dissatisfaction. The perception is mostly positive, as reflected in Figure 7. However, communication about the

relevance and benefits of audits needs to be improved to ensure broader understanding and appreciation.

Figura 7. Auditorías periódicas para supervisar y evaluar la gestión de la correspondencia.

Nota: La grafica muestra la necesidad de continuar con las auditorías de la AC de la UTT.

The reliability result obtained using the Cronbach's alpha method for the analyzed data set shows a value of 0.94, indicating excellent internal consistency in the measurement. This coefficient was calculated on a total of 78 items, suggesting that the instrument's variables are highly consistent with each other, ensuring high reliability in the results obtained through the SPSS system. The value close to 1.0 reinforces the validity of the responses, allowing confidence in the accuracy of the instruments used in the assessment, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Cronbach's alpha coefficient

Cronbach's alpha	Number of elements
0.94	78

DISCUSSION

Regarding document preservation and the current challenges at the UTT, Mero et al. (2021) highlight that adequate document management is essential for preserving history and institutional knowledge. At the Universidad Tecnológica de Tulancingo (UTT), improving this aspect would not only allow for better organization of documents but also prevent the loss of valuable information, which Pilataxi (2020) considers essential to guarantee the authenticity and reliability of documents. To this end, it is recommended that the Archives Law be applied throughout the management process, promoting orderly handling in compliance with legal provisions.

Coordinated processes in the absence of structure, according to Sosa (2022), are essential to have organized and

homogeneous processes to manage information efficiently. At the UTT, the lack of standardized systems could be generating difficulties that can be solved by adopting the Institutional Archive System (IAS), as suggested by Sosa et al. (2022). Although the use of a validated system does not in itself guarantee efficient management, compliance with the Law ensures the proper functioning of the correspondence archive (CA).

Using modern web systems versus centralization. Santos (2020) developed a web-based system that optimizes correspondence management and favors decision-making. The UTT could implement a similar tool to more effectively centralize and coordinate its correspondence, solving problems such as those identified by Balderas et al. (2022) at CONALEP Tabasco, where the absence of a system made error detection difficult.

Transparency in management in the presence of control problems. Castillo et al. (2021) state that an efficient documentation system fosters transparency and accountability. At the UTT, adopting a similar system could improve institutional credibility and strengthen internal and external relations, contributing to the achievement of its educational objectives.

Optimizing resources versus wasting time and effort. The Royal Spanish Academy (RAE, 2024) defines optimization as the search for the best way to perform a task. Likewise, Vinueza (2020) and Cuesta (2023) emphasize that optimizing resources is vital to improving services. The UTT can leverage these insights to make more efficient use of its personnel and technology, thereby achieving superior administrative performance.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The CA is an essential process in any organization, as it ensures efficient and orderly communication between different departments and with the external environment. Through proper management of incoming and outgoing correspondence, a constant flow of information is maintained and decision-making is facilitated. Established procedures for recording, classifying, distributing, and archiving documents optimize time and resources, while also ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of information.

CA is fundamental to the functioning of any organization. Proper management of incoming and outgoing correspondence ensures that information flows efficiently and orderly between different departments and with the external context. This allows for informed and timely decisions, which in turn improves the organization's efficiency and productivity.

Established procedures for recording, classifying, distributing, and archiving documents are essential for optimizing time and resources. These procedures include:

Recording incoming and outgoing correspondence is crucial for maintaining proper document control. This allows you to track correspondence and ensure it is handled in a timely manner.

Correspondence classification helps organize documents so that they are easily accessible, making it easier to search for and retrieve information when needed.

Distributing correspondence to the appropriate departments or individuals ensures that information reaches the right hands in a timely manner.

CA is essential for maintaining a historical record of documents, it is important for future reference and to comply with legal and regulatory requirements.

Proposals for Solutions or Improvements.

- Implementation of an Automated Document Management System through processes: Creating an automated and centralized document management system through processes can significantly improve efficiency in document location and retrieval. An automated version control system and collaboration tools can reduce error rates and optimize response times. Document standardized procedures for correspondence management ensure that all departments follow the same guidelines. This will improve consistency and reduce variability in correspondence handling.

- Staff Training and Awareness: Organize workshops and training sessions for staff on the importance and use of correspondence management. This will help reduce the number of respondents who are indifferent or disagree with current procedures, thereby improving the perception and practice of document management in the organization. Training should include the use of new technological tools and adherence to established procedures.

- Audits and Constant Monitoring: Conduct periodic audits and establish a continuous monitoring system to assess compliance with document management procedures. This will identify areas for improvement and ensure that best practices are maintained over time. Tracking key indicators, such as response time and error rate, will help measure the system's effectiveness and make adjustments when necessary. Implementing a continuous review of document management processes will help identify areas for improvement and adapt to changing organizational needs. This includes staff feedback and updating the procedures and tools used in correspondence management.

- User Satisfaction Assessment: Implement periodic surveys to assess employee satisfaction with the correspondence management system. This will allow you to identify areas for improvement from the user perspective and adjust processes based on their needs and expectations.

- Improve Internal Communication: Create effective communication channels to inform employees about the status and changes to correspondence management

“Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica De Tulancingo”

procedures; this could include newsletters, regular meetings, and an updated intranet.

- Allocation of Adequate Resources: Ensure that the departments involved in correspondence management have the necessary resources, both human and technological, to carry out their tasks efficiently.
- Implementation of Performance Indicators: Establish key performance indicators specific to mail management, such as response time and sorting accuracy. Regular monitoring of these indicators will help measure the system's efficiency and effectiveness. As shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9.UTT Improvement Proposals Outline

Note: Proposals for improvement derived from research conducted at UTT.

REFERENCES

1. Balderas, M., Gómez, J., Garrido, J., Hernández, A., Jesús, J. (2022) Modelo de aplicación web para la automatización de la gestión de correspondencia en CONALEP Tabasco. *Innovación y Desarrollo Tecnológico Revista Digital. Tecnológico Nacional de México Campus Villahermosa. División de Estudios de Posgrado e Investigación.* 14(3) https://iydt.wordpress.com/wpcontent/uploads/2022/05/3_11_modelo-de-aplicacion-web-para-la-automatizacion-de-la-gestion-de-correspondencia-en-conalep-tabasco.pdf
2. Berdugo, L. (2016) Análisis de los sistemas de gestión documental que existen actualmente en Colombia que cumplen con la legislación vigente para empresas públicas de acuerdo con el programa de gestión documental. Universidad Militar Nueva Granada especialización de alta gerencia. Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y Administrativas Bogotá D.C. <https://repository.unimilitar.edu.co/server/api/core/bit>

streams/a034819a-50a3-4d88-a00b-f3e480bfde8e/content

3. Cázquez C. (2020) Gestión documental en el archivo central, para fortalecer un plan de mejoras de la Universidad Técnica del Norte en el periodo 2018-2019. Universidad Técnica del Norte. Facultad de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología FECYT. <https://repositorio.utn.edu.ec/bitstream/123456789/10612/2/05%20FECYT%203685%20TRABAJO%20GRADO.pdf>
4. Castillo, J., Mena, M., Torres, D. (2021) Propuesta de requisitos generales para el sistema de gestión documental de la Universidad de La Habana. *Revista Cubana de Información en Ciencias de la Salud.* 32(1) http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?pid=S2307-21132021000100005&script=sci_arttext&tlng=pt
5. Contreras Orozco, L. (2010). La calidad en la gestión como factor de cambio institucional en las organizaciones gubernamentales del Estado de México. *Convergencia Revista de Ciencias Sociales,* 17(53), 245-268. https://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?script=sci_artext&pid=S1405-14352010000200012
6. Cuesta, A., Delgado, M., Fleitas, S., Linares, M. (2023) Optimización del capital humano por innovación en procesos de gestión humana y del conocimiento. *Anales de la Academia de Ciencias de Cuba.* 13(1) Scielo http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?pid=S2304-01062023000100015&script=sci_arttext&tlng=en
7. Fernandini, M. (2021) Comunicación interna y la gestión organizacional en una institución educativa de Chorrillos, 2021. Universidad César Vallejo. Escuela de Posgrado. Programa Académico de Maestría en Administración de la Educación. https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/bitstream/handle/20.500.12692/78403/Fernandini_ZMP-SD.pdf?sequence=8&isAllowed=y
8. Henao, A. E. P. (2020). La comunicación organizacional en la gestión empresarial: retos y oportunidades en el escenario digital. *Revista GEON: Gestión-Organización-Negocios,* 7(1), 9-25. Recuperado de <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=4j94deEA-AAAJ&hl=es>.
9. Hernández, F. (2020) Análisis del alcance e implicaciones del patrimonio de los archivos en México para la investigación social. Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco. *Revista San Gregorio.* 39 74-86 <http://scielo.senescyt.gob.ec/pdf/rsan/n39/2528-7907-rsan-39-00074.pdf>
10. Hernández Rojas, F. J. (2015). Prácticas de gestión organizacional innovadoras en el sector público: caso:

“Organizational Management Strategies at the Executive Level for the Optimization of Correspondence Administration (Study Case) Universidad Tecnológica De Tulancingo”

- innovación gerencial en la división de impuestos del distrito de Cartagena de Indias. Universidad Tecnológica de Bolívar
<https://repositorio.utb.edu.co/bitstream/handle/20.500.12585/3517/0068222.pdf?sequence=1>
11. Kyocera Document Solutions México. (2020). Cómo mejorar la gestión documental con inteligencia artificial. Recuperado de <https://www.kyoceradocumentsolutions.mx/es/insights/insights-hub/articles/como-la-inteligencia-artificial-mejora-la-gestion-documental.html>
 12. Lacunza, A., Clark, R., Marafuschi, M. (2021) La gestión documental electrónica en la UNLP. El camino hacia el expediente electrónico. Revista es. Universidad Nacional de la Plata. 1(1y2)
<https://revistas.unlp.edu.ar/ES/article/view/13086>
 13. La Era Digital. (2024). Inteligencia Artificial en los Sistemas de Gestión Documental. Recuperado de [<https://laeradigital.blog/2024/10/28/inteligencia-artificial-en-los-sistemas-de-gestion-documental/>](<https://laeradigital.blog/2024/10/28/inteligencia-artificial-en-los-sistemas-de-gestion-document>)
 14. Medina, WMG (2021). Gestión estratégica, factor clave para el éxito organizacional. SUMMA Revista Disciplinaria En Ciencias Económicas y Sociales, 3 (2). <https://doi.org/10.47666/summa.3.2.40>
 15. Mero, D., García, L., Cobacango, J. (2021) Gestión Documental orientada a la conservación de los documentos en el archivo histórico de la Universidad técnica de Manabí. Revista de ciencias humanísticas y Sociales 6, 98-107
<https://revistas.utm.edu.ec/index.php/Rehuso/article/view/1684>
 16. Mocetón, A., Pinzón, H. (2022) La gestión documental y su importancia en las entidades públicas y privadas Departamento de gestión documental: Fundación universitaria para el desarrollo humano UNINPAHU. Escuela Superior de Administración Pública.
<https://repositoriocdim.esap.edu.co/bitstream/handle/20.500.14471/26632/ANGIE%20LIZETH%20JIM%20c3%89NEZ%20MOCET%c3%93N.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
 17. Pilataxi, H. (2020) Gestión documental y técnicas de archivo en la unidad educativa Juan Montalvo Mixta en la parroquia González Suárez Cantón Otavalo año 2019. Universidad Técnica del Norte. Facultad de Educación Ciencia y Tecnología FECYT.
<https://repositorio.utm.edu.ec/bitstream/123456789/10608/2/05%20FECYT%203684%20TRABAJO%20GRADO.pdf>
 18. Ramírez, R. I., Antequera, R. R., Raby, N. D. L., & Antúnez, J. V. V. (2023). Gestión organizacional en coordinaciones universitarias de postgrados. Formación Universitaria, 16(3), 73–82.
<https://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-50062023000300073>
 19. Real Academia Española (2024). Diccionario del estudiante, <https://www.rae.es/diccionario-estudiante/gesti%C3%B3n>
 20. Riera, E. (2020) Sistema de gestión documental para la empresa Logikard. Revista Odigos. Universidad Israel. 1(3)
<https://revista.uisrael.edu.ec/index.php/ro/article/view/371/184>
 21. Rodríguez, D. (2023) Liferder. Unidad de Correspondencia. <https://www.liferder.com/unidad-de-correspondencia/>
 22. Rojas, Y., Molina, A., Angúlo, L. (2021) Optimización para los motores de búsqueda (SEO) y la garantía de posicionamiento en los buscadores. Punto de Vista. Universidad de Ciencias Médicas de Cienfuegos
<https://www.medigraphic.com/pdfs/medisur/msu-2021/msu211u.pdf>
 23. Rojas Jorquera, F. (2020). Modelo de gestión y análisis de correspondencia presidencial: un enfoque desde la eficiencia operacional y la gestión inteligente de datos. Universidad del Desarrollo.
<https://repositorio.udd.cl/bitstreams/ffbd435c-68aa-48c9-bb2e-febac0a65c89/download>
 24. Roque, A. (2012). Diseño de un modelo de sistema integral de documentación para las Instituciones de Educación Superior: el caso práctico de la Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo. Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo. Instituto de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades. Maestría en Ciencias Sociales.
<http://dgsa.uaeh.edu.mx:8080/bibliotecadigital/handle/231104/2862>
 25. Salazar, J., Vergara, A., Zamora, S., Navarrete, A. (2022) Estrategias para la optimización de la gestión administrativa de una empresa constructora usando el balanced scorecard. Revista científica RES NON VERBA. Universidad Tecnológica ECOTEC, Samborondón, Ecuador. 12(1) 56-73
<https://revistas.ecotec.edu.ec/index.php/rnv/article/view/623/416>
 26. Santos, Y. (2020). Sistema de Gestión de Correspondencia – Vía Web Caso: Área Ciencias Económicas, Financieras y Administrativas-Universidad Pública el Alto. Universidad del Tercer Milenio.
<https://repositorio.upea.bo/jspui/bitstream/123456789/136/1/%e2%80%9cSISTEMA%20DE%20GESTI%c3%93N%20DE%20CORRESPONDENCIA.pdf>
 27. Soria, D., Díaz, L. (2020) Diseño de un sistema de gestión documental para uso interno en la Universidad

- de Otavalo. Universidad de Otavalo. Ecuador 16(73)
http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?pid=S1990-86442020000200157&script=sci_arttext
28. Sosa, C., Caballero, F., Guzmán, J., Perales, C. (2022). Gestión documental a través del Sistema Institucional de Archivos. Una aproximación desde el orden normativo mexicano. *Revista General de Información y Documentación*, 32(1), 243-265. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Frida-Rico/publication/362132813_Gestion_documental_a_traves_del_Sistema_Institucional_de_Archivos_Una_aproximacion_desde_el_orden_normativo_mexicano/links/62d9c2d13c7d1903169dee5d/Gestion-documental-a-traves-del-Sistema-Institucional-de-Archivos-Una-aproximacion-desde-el-orden-normativo-mexicano.pdf
 29. Sosa, C., González N. (2022) El sistema institucional de archivos y su aplicabilidad en la gestión del conocimiento en las organizaciones. *Asesorías y Tutorías para la Investigación Científica en la Educación Puig-Salabarría S.C. Revista Dilemas Contemporáneos: Educación Política y Valores*. 3(60) <https://dilemascontemporaneoseduccionpoliticaayvalores.com/index.php/dilemas/article/view/3231/3214>
 30. Tineo, CC y Mehan, JMM (2021). TIC, comunicación organizacional en la gestión de los directivos. *UCV HACER*, 10 (2). <https://doi.org/10.18050/revucvhacer.v10n2a3>
 31. Vinueza, J., Robalino, R. (2020) La optimización y el control interno en el uso de los recursos públicos en la mejora de la gestión administrativa. *Revista científica ciencias económicas y empresariales*. 16(5) 14-38 <https://fipcaec.com/index.php/fipcaec/article/view/158/240>